

Mining Specification Parameters for Multi-Class Classification

Edgar Aguilar¹, Ezio Bartocci², Cristinel Mateis¹,
Eleonora Nesterini^{1,2}, and Dejan Nickovic²

¹ AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Vienna, Austria

² TU Wien, Vienna, Austria

Abstract. We present a method for mining parameters of temporal specifications for signal classification. Given a parametric formula and a set of labeled traces, we find one parameter valuation for each class and use it to instantiate the specification template. The resulting formula characterizes the signals in a class by discriminating them from signals of other classes. We propose a two-step approach: first, for each class, we approximate its validity domain, which is the region of the valuations that render the formula satisfied. Second, we select from each validity domain the valuation that maximizes the distance from the validity domain of other classes. We provide a statistical guarantee that the selected parameter valuation is at a bounded distance from being optimal. Finally, we validate our approach on three case studies from different application domains.

Keywords: Specification mining · Signal Temporal Logic · Classification.

1 Introduction

Formal specifications are essential during system design, verification, and operation. They allow a precise and unambiguous exchange of requirements between engineering teams, enable rigorous verification of critical system components, and translate into test oracles and runtime monitors during system execution.

Cyber-physical systems (CPS) include physical parts whose properties are only partially known at design time. Generally, an engineer may expect a system to act a certain way without knowing the exact numerical values that characterize the system’s behavior. For instance, an engineer may know that the system response to a step input is an overshoot while ignoring its delay from the input or its amplitude. We can express this partial knowledge about the intended property using a parameterized specification template. Characterizing the actual parameters is a challenging task that requires the help of an automated tool.

Related work. Specification mining [3] is an emerging area of research in the field of CPS motivated by the need to analyze and explain the massive amount of data gathered from these systems while interacting with the environment. The vast majority of the available approaches employ Signal Temporal Logic (STL) [14] as the formal specification language for mining requirements in CPS [5, 20]. Parametric Signal Temporal Logic (PSTL) [1] is a parametric extension of STL in which parameters replace

both threshold constants in numerical predicates and time bounds in temporal operators. Some works address the problem of learning the optimal parameters for a given candidate template formula [1, 2, 10], while others learn both the structure and the parameters [5, 6, 11, 16]. These approaches focus on learning an STL formula using only positive examples of trajectories [11] or positive and negative examples [2, 16].

In this paper, we broaden the applicability of STL specification mining to the multi-class classification problem: we aim to find the set of parameters for given PSTL template formulas that can discriminate multiple classes of trajectories. We assume a set of labeled traces and characterize each class of traces with an STL formula. A final classifier leverages STL quantitative semantics to evaluate how robustly a trace satisfies/violates each specification and consequently predicts the trace’s label.

Recently, also other papers [13, 15] considered a similar task. However, both works limit the space of mined specifications to STL fragments, reducing the resulting expressiveness. Moreover, they are both template-free methods; namely, they mine both the formula template and its numerical predicates. Such an approach is a double-edged sword: on the one hand, template-free methods do not require prior knowledge, but, on the other hand, they do not allow embedding information in the procedure and thus steer the search toward specific properties that are relevant in a particular application. Conversely, we aim to tackle the complementary task of mining parameters without any restrictions on STL grammar.

Our contribution. In this paper, we propose a family of methods for mining PSTL parameters for multi-class classification. We assume a PSTL template associated with each labeled class of signals and choose the parameters in each template to maximize discrimination from the signals with the other labels. We devise a two-step approach to this problem. For each labeled class of signals, we first approximate two validity domains, one for the signals belonging to that class and one for all other signals. The *validity domain* is the region of the parameter space that instantiates satisfied specifications from a given template. In the second step, we select a parameter instantiation within the first validity domain and maximize its distance from the other one. We return both the set of instantiated STL specifications (one for each class) and a classifier that combines them. The former helps gain insights into what discriminates one class from the others. At the same time, the latter is essential to performing the classification task and, in particular, to classifying new unlabeled traces.

One of the main advantages of the proposed methods is that they do not require any assumptions regarding the monotonicity of parameters. Monotonicity is a common restriction in the specification mining literature because it significantly simplifies the geometry of the resulting validity domains and thus leads to a much more tractable problem. Additionally, we show that our selection of parameter valuations has a statistical guarantee of being optimal. We implement our approach in a publicly available prototype tool and evaluate it on three case studies from different application domains.

2 Preliminaries

A *time series* $\mathbf{x} = (t_1, x_1), (t_2, x_2), \dots, (t_l, x_l)$ is a finite sequence of (time, value) pairs, where $t_1 = 0$, $t_i < t_{i+1}$ for every $i \in \{1, \dots, l - 1\}$, and $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^k$ is a vector

of real values. We denote by $|\mathbf{x}| = l$ the length of \mathbf{x} . We will abuse notation, and also denote by \mathbf{x} the signal $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$, such that $\mathbf{x}(t) = x_i$ if $t \in [t_i, t_{i+1})$ with $i < l$, or $\mathbf{x}(t) = x_l$ if $t \geq t_l$.

The distance between a point $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and a (non-empty) set $\mathcal{Q} \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ is defined as:

$$d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{Q}) = \inf\{\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}) \mid \mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{Q}\}, \quad (1)$$

where $\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q})$ is the Euclidean distance in \mathbb{R}^k . To compute the *distance* from one set to another, we consider the so-called “directed Hausdorff distance”, defined by:

$$D(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q}) = \sup\{d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{Q}) \mid \mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}\}. \quad (2)$$

We observe that function D is not a proper distance because it is not necessarily symmetric. Intuitively, the function computes the longest distance from a point in \mathcal{V} and its closest point in \mathcal{Q} . An illustration of how function D works and how it is related to the Hausdorff distance is depicted in Fig. 1.

Signal Temporal Logic (STL) [14] is a specification language used to express continuous temporal properties over real-valued signals. The syntax of STL is given by the grammar:

$$\varphi := \mathbf{true} \mid f(\mathbf{x}) > 0 \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2 \mid \varphi_1 \mathbf{U}_I \varphi_2$$

where \mathbf{true} is the Boolean true constant, $f(\mathbf{x}) > 0$ is an atomic proposition with $f: \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, \neg is the Boolean negation, \wedge is the Boolean conjunction, and \mathbf{U}_I is the *until* operator defined over the interval I in $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. The interval I is generally omitted if $I = [0, \infty)$. The *finally* \mathbf{F} and *globally* \mathbf{G} operators can be derived as follows: $\mathbf{F}_I \varphi := \mathbf{true} \mathbf{U}_I \varphi$ and $\mathbf{G}_I \varphi := \neg \mathbf{F}_I \neg \varphi$.

The quantitative semantics of STL [7] is defined in terms of the *robustness function* ρ that has as arguments: the STL specification φ , the signal \mathbf{x} and the time t . The value $\rho(\varphi, \mathbf{x}, t)$ is defined inductively as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\mathbf{true}, \mathbf{x}, t) &= +\infty \\ \rho(f(\mathbf{x}) > 0, \mathbf{x}, t) &= f(\mathbf{x}(t)) \\ \rho(\neg\varphi, \mathbf{x}, t) &= -\rho(\varphi, \mathbf{x}, t) \\ \rho(\varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2, \mathbf{x}, t) &= \min(\rho(\varphi_1, \mathbf{x}, t), \rho(\varphi_2, \mathbf{x}, t)) \\ \rho(\varphi_1 \mathbf{U}_I \varphi_2, \mathbf{x}, t) &= \sup_{t' \in t \oplus I} \left(\min(\rho(\varphi_2, \mathbf{x}, t'), \inf_{t'' \in (t, t')} (\rho(\varphi_1, \mathbf{x}, t'')) \right) \end{aligned}$$

We indicate $\rho(\varphi, \mathbf{x}, 0)$ by $\rho(\varphi; \mathbf{x})$. The STL quantitative semantics is *sound*, i.e., when $\rho(\varphi, \mathbf{x}, t) > 0$ the signal \mathbf{x} satisfies φ , while when $\rho(\varphi, \mathbf{x}, t) < 0$ it violates it.

Fig. 1. The Hausdorff distance D_H between sets \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{Q} is defined as: $D_H(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q}) := \max\{D(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q}), D(\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{V})\}$. In the above example, $D(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q}) = d(\bar{\mathbf{v}}, \mathcal{Q})$, $D(\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{V}) = d(\bar{\mathbf{q}}, \mathcal{V})$, and $D_H(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q}) = D(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Q})$.

A *PSTL template* is an STL formula where some temporal or magnitude values are replaced by parameter symbols [1]. If m is the number of different parameter symbols in a PSTL formula, we indicate by $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ the set of parameter symbols and with \mathcal{W} the *parameter space*, that is the set of values that parameter symbols may assume. In our case, \mathcal{W} is a closed hyperbox in \mathbb{R}^m , that is

$$\mathcal{W} = \prod_{i=1}^m [a_i, b_i], \quad (3)$$

where, for every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, a_i and b_i are scalar values in \mathbb{R} and $b_i > a_i$. A *parameter valuation* $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{W}$ maps a PSTL formula φ into the STL formula $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}}$ obtained from φ by replacing its parameter symbols with \mathbf{v} . For example, given the template $\varphi = \mathbf{G}_{[T_1, T_2]}(x \geq k)$, where T_1 and T_2 are temporal parameters and k is a magnitude parameter, if $\mathbf{v} = (0, 2, 3.5)$, then the resulting STL formula $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}}$ is $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{G}_{[0, 2]}(x \geq 3.5)$. With a little abuse of notation, we will occasionally write that a signal \mathbf{x} satisfies/violates a parameter valuation \mathbf{v} to mean that \mathbf{x} satisfies/violates the specification $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}}$.

Given a signal \mathbf{x} and a PSTL formula φ , the *validity domain* $\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{x}, \varphi) \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ is defined as the set of all parameter valuations \mathbf{v} that generate STL formulas $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}}$ satisfied by the signal \mathbf{x} . In the previous example, if the signal \mathbf{x} satisfies the STL specification $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{G}_{[0, 2]}(x \geq 3.5)$, then $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}(\mathbf{x}, \varphi)$. The validity domain of a finite set \mathcal{S} of signals corresponds to the intersection of all validity domains of signals in the set \mathcal{S} . In other words, $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{S}, \varphi)$ if and only if $\varphi_{\mathbf{v}}$ is satisfied by all signals in \mathcal{S} .

3 Problem Description

Hypotheses. We assume that two classes of time-series are given: \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . The restriction to two classes is for the sake of a simpler description: in Section 4.3, we show how the proposed method is extended to an arbitrary number of classes. In addition, the user provides a PSTL template for each class of signals. We first assume the template φ is the same for both classes and then, in Section 4.2, we present the generalization to different templates. Finally, we assume that the lower/upper bounds on parameter values are available, so the values of a_i and b_i in Eq. (3) are known for all $i = 1, \dots, m$.

Goal. Our goal is to discriminate classes \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 using formula φ . To do so, we need to find two parameters valuations \mathbf{v}_1^* and \mathbf{v}_2^* for φ such that they characterize the two sets of time series and *best* discriminate between them. The term *best* refers to the following optimality criteria. We denote by \mathcal{V}_i the validity domain $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{S}_i, \varphi)$ of class \mathcal{S}_i with respect to φ whenever φ is clear from the context.

Definition 1 *An optimal parameter valuation \mathbf{v}_1^* for \mathcal{S}_1 with respect to \mathcal{S}_2 is such that:*

1. $\mathbf{v}_1^* \in \mathcal{V}_1$;
2. $d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}_1$,

where d is the point-set distance defined in (1).

The first condition ensures that all time series in \mathcal{S}_1 satisfy the STL formula $\varphi_{v_1^*}$, while the second one forces v_1^* to be the point in \mathcal{V}_1 that is the *furthest* from the other class satisfaction region. In other words, the first condition makes $\varphi_{v_1^*}$ a characterization of time series in \mathcal{S}_1 , while the second condition renders $\varphi_{v_1^*}$ one of the *best* instantiations of φ for discriminating \mathcal{S}_1 from \mathcal{S}_2 (the optimal point is not necessarily unique). The definition of v_2^* for time series in class \mathcal{S}_2 is analogous.

In some extreme cases, we observe that the given definition of an optimal point is meaningless because the Hausdorff distance between the two validity domains is zero (for example, if the two validity domains are identical or one validity domain is a subset of the other). This eventuality may happen when the template φ is not suitable for discriminating the two classes; in this case, there is no choice of the parameter valuations that would help with the classification. The only reasonable possibility is that the user changes the PSTL template. Section 5 shows an example of this instance.

Once our procedure identifies the parameter valuations, we need to perform the classification. We remind that the validity domain of a class is the intersection of the validity domains of all signals belonging to that class. It follows that a signal \mathbf{x} belonging to \mathcal{S}_2 does not necessarily violate φ_v with $v \in \mathcal{V}_1 \setminus \mathcal{V}_2$. As a consequence, it may happen that \mathbf{x} satisfies both $\varphi_{v_1^*}$ and $\varphi_{v_2^*}$. Hence, we cannot simply use the Boolean satisfaction of $\varphi_{v_1^*}$ and $\varphi_{v_2^*}$ to predict the signal’s label. For this reason, we use the quantitative semantics of STL and classify a signal \mathbf{x} in class 1 if $\rho(\varphi_{v_1^*}; \mathbf{x}) \geq \rho(\varphi_{v_2^*}; \mathbf{x})$ and in class 2 otherwise, being ρ the robustness function defined in Section 2.

4 Our Approach

We propose a two-step approach to address the problem of Section 3: for each class, we compute (i) an over-approximation $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ of its validity domain \mathcal{V} , and (ii) an approximation of the *optimal* point in the validity domain. For the approximation of the validity domains, we divide the parameter space \mathcal{W} into a lattice of cells. We present two methods: one in which the cell resolution is fixed and one in which it is adaptive. We first consider the case in which the same PSTL template is associated with the two different classes of signals (Sections 4.1). Then, we extend our approach to allow two different PSTL templates (Section 4.2) and an arbitrary number of classes (Section 4.3). The proofs are shown in the Appendix.

4.1 Binary Satisfaction

Fixed Granularity with Binary Satisfaction (FixedBin) We first describe how we compute the approximation $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ of a validity domain \mathcal{V} (Algorithm 1). The parameter space \mathcal{W} is divided into a partition \mathcal{C} of axis-aligned closed-hyperboxes having all the same size that we call *cells* (line 2). Each cell is then evaluated separately, and included in the over-approximation $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ only if it is found a parameter valuation v inside the cell such that the STL formula φ_v is satisfied by all time series in the class under study. If, after N trials, no valid parameter valuation is found, then the cell is not included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$.

We observe that $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ is intended to be an over-approximation of \mathcal{V} . However, it is possible that a cell $C \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ is not included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ even though there exists a valuation

$v \in C$ in the cell that is also included in \mathcal{V} . This can happen because we decide whether C shall be included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ based on a finite number N of samples in C . It follows that the choice of N in Algorithm 1 affects the likelihood of a cell that has non-empty intersection with the true validity domain to be included in the over-approximation, as stated by Lemma 1.

Algorithm 1: Validity domain approximation with *FixedBin*

Input: PSTL template φ , set of signals \mathcal{S} , parameter space \mathcal{W} , number of trials N

Output: Approximated validity domain $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$

```

1  $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2  $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \text{cell\_partition}(\mathcal{W})$ 
3 foreach  $C \in \mathcal{C}$  do
4   for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
5      $v \leftarrow \text{uniform}(C)$ 
6     flag  $\leftarrow$  true
7     foreach  $x \in \mathcal{S}$  do
8       if  $x \not\models \varphi_v$  then
9         flag  $\leftarrow$  false
10        break
11     if flag then
12        $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \leftarrow \hat{\mathcal{V}} \cup C$ 
13       break
14 return  $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ 

```

Algorithm 2: Validity domain approximation using *AdaBin*.

Input: PSTL template φ , set of signals \mathcal{S} , cell C , approx. validity domain $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$, # trials N , threshold on the concentration of satisfied parameter valuation h

Output: New approximation for $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$

```

1 counter  $\leftarrow$  0
2 for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
3    $v \leftarrow \text{uniform}(C)$ 
4   flag  $\leftarrow$  true
5   foreach  $x \in \mathcal{S}$  do
6     if  $x \not\models \varphi_v$  then
7       flag  $\leftarrow$  false
8       break
9   if flag then counter  $\leftarrow$  counter + 1
10 if  $\frac{\text{counter}}{N} \geq h$  then return  $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \cup C$ 
11 else if counter = 0 then return  $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ 
12 else if size( $C$ ) =  $g$  then return  $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \cup C$ 
13 else
14    $C_1, \dots, C_{2^m} \leftarrow \text{split}(C)$ 
15   for  $j = 1, \dots, 2^m$  do
16      $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \leftarrow \text{Algorithm2}(\varphi, \mathcal{S}, C_j, \hat{\mathcal{V}}, N, h)$ 
17 return  $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ 

```

Lemma 1 (Choice of N). *Let \mathcal{V} be a validity domain, C a cell not included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ based on N random samples. If $N \geq \log_{1-p_0}(\alpha)$ with $p_0, \alpha \in (0, 1)$, then the probability that C contains points in \mathcal{V} is smaller than p_0 with confidence $1 - \alpha$.*

As a concrete example, let us set $p_0 = 0.01$ and $\alpha = 0.05$. In this setting, we need to examine $N \geq \log_{(1-p_0)} \alpha = \log_{0.99}(0.05) = 298$ parameter valuations to conclude with confidence 95% that the proportion of satisfied parameter valuations in the cell is less than 1%.

Once we have computed both $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$, we select the point \hat{v}_1 in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ such that \hat{v}_1 and $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$ have maximum distance. In other words, we select \hat{v}_1 such that $d(\hat{v}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) = D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2)$, where the functions d and D are defined in (1) and (2), respectively. To prove the existence of such a point \hat{v}_1 , we need to show that $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ is a compact set, so that the supremum in definition (2) is in fact a maximum. Since the cells used to

approximate \mathcal{V}_1 are closed-hyperboxes, $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ is also a closed set (it is finite union of closed sets). Moreover, $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ is a bounded set because it is a subset of the parameter space \mathcal{W} that is bounded by hypothesis. Finally, being a closed and bounded set in \mathbb{R}^m , $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ is compact. The same reasoning is applied to the choice of $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_2$ in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$.

The following theorem relates the selected parameter valuation to an optimal one, showing that the difference of their respective distances to the other class validity domain is upper-bounded by the cells' size. Hence, it can be arbitrarily reduced.

Theorem 1 (Optimality). *Let \mathcal{V}_1 and \mathcal{V}_2 be the validity domains for classes \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . Let $i \in \{1, 2\}$, \mathbf{v}_i^* be an optimal parameter valuation for class i , $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_i$ be the approximation of \mathcal{V}_i using cell resolution given by vector $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^m$, $N \geq \log_{1-p_0}(\alpha)$, and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ the parameter valuation found with FixedBin. Then, the difference of the distances from $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ and from \mathbf{v}_i^* to the other class validity domain is bounded by the cell resolution:*

$$|d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i, \mathcal{V}_{(i \bmod 2)+1}) - d(\mathbf{v}_i^*, \mathcal{V}_{(i \bmod 2)+1})| \leq \|\mathbf{g}\| \quad (4)$$

with probability $1 - p_0$ and confidence $1 - \alpha$.

Finally, the complexity of the algorithm is reported in the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (Complexity). *Let n be the total number of signals and let m be the number of different parameter symbols in the PSTL template φ . Let $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^m$ be the vector that contains the minimal sizes of the cells and let the parameter space be $\mathcal{W} = \prod_{i=1}^m [a_i, b_i]$ as in Eq. (3). Then, the total number L of monitors is exponential in m and linear in n . In particular,*

$$L \leq \left(\max_{i=1, \dots, m} \left\lceil \frac{b_i - a_i}{g_i} \right\rceil \right)^m \cdot (N \cdot n) = \mathcal{O}(M^m) \cdot \mathcal{O}(n),$$

where N is the maximum number of parameter valuations to be evaluated in every cell and M is a suitable positive number.

Adaptive Granularity with Binary Satisfaction (AdaBin) We present an alternative to compute over-approximations of validity domains using an adaptive cell resolution that exploits binary search (Algorithm 2).

The algorithm starts considering an initial empty approximation of the validity domain ($\hat{\mathcal{V}} \leftarrow \emptyset$), and the whole parameter space as a single cell ($C \leftarrow \mathcal{W}$). One cell at a time is then evaluated with three possible outcomes: (i) the cell is added to the approximation of the validity domain; (ii) the cell is not added to the approximation of the validity domain; (iii) the cell is split. The first two scenarios happen, respectively, when the cell presents a high concentration h of satisfied parameter valuations (line 10), or when no satisfied parameter valuations are found (line 11). Otherwise, reminding that m is the number of parameter symbols in the template φ , the cell is split into 2^m new cells generated by dividing each edge into two (at its middle point). When the minimal cell size is reached (line 12), we perform (i) if at least one satisfied parameter valuation is found. The minimal cell resolution \mathbf{g} has to be reached by doing the same amount of splits in all parameter dimensions. Recalling the representation of parameter space \mathcal{W} in Eq. (3), it follows that there must exist a natural number k such that

$$b_i - a_i = 2^k \cdot g_i \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (5)$$

Monotonic variant The *monotonic variant* of the previous methods is introduced to speed up the computation of the validity domain approximations in case the parametric STL template is monotonic with respect to all its parameters. A PSTL formula φ is *monotonically increasing* (or *decreasing*) with respect to its parameter p_i , if, for every pair of valuations w_i and w'_i such that $w_i \leq w'_i$ (or $w_i \geq w'_i$) and for every signal \mathbf{x} , $\rho(\varphi_{\mathbf{v}, w_i}; \mathbf{x}) \leq \rho(\varphi_{\mathbf{v}, w'_i}; \mathbf{x})$, where \mathbf{v} corresponds to a generic valuation of the other parameters in φ .

For a PSTL formula φ that is monotonic with respect to all its parameters, we define the *lowest point* and the *highest point* of a cell C . The cells that we use to approximate the parameter space are closed hyperboxes in \mathbb{R}^m ; hence, they are representable as $C = \prod_{i=1}^m [q_i, Q_i]$, where $q_i, Q_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and $q_i < Q_i$ for every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. The *lowest point* in C is the point that is the most likely to be violated, namely the vector in \mathbb{R}^m whose i -th component is q_i if φ is increasing with respect to parameter p_i , or Q_i if φ is decreasing with respect to p_i . Conversely, the *highest point* of a cell C is the point which is most likely to be satisfied, being the vector in \mathbb{R}^m whose i -th component is Q_i if φ is increasing with respect to parameter p_i , or q_i if φ is decreasing with respect to p_i .

The following equivalences are the bases of the monotonic variant methods, allowing for a complete evaluation of a cell through the study of only these two special parameter valuations: (i) all parameter valuations in a cell are violated if and only if its *highest point* is violated, and (ii) all parameter valuations in a cell are satisfied if and only if its *lowest point* is satisfied.

Remark 1 *If the PSTL template is monotonic with respect to all its parameters, then (4) holds deterministically because the statistical guarantee in Lemma 1 is not needed for the evaluation of the cell if highest and lowest points are studied.*

4.2 Different templates

The following extension should be applied when the user wants to describe the two classes of signals with different PSTL templates. Let φ_1 represent the temporal behavior of time series in class \mathcal{S}_1 and φ_2 for class \mathcal{S}_2 . The parameter valuation \hat{v}_1 is chosen in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}(\mathcal{S}_1, \varphi_1)$ to maximize the distance from $\hat{\mathcal{V}}(\mathcal{S}_2, \varphi_1)$ and is used to instantiate the PSTL template φ_1 for the characterization of \mathcal{S}_1 . Analogously, \hat{v}_2 will instantiate φ_2 to characterize \mathcal{S}_2 by discriminating $\hat{\mathcal{V}}(\mathcal{S}_2, \varphi_2)$ from $\hat{\mathcal{V}}(\mathcal{S}_1, \varphi_2)$. In other words, the computation of \hat{v}_1 and \hat{v}_2 is carried out separately by applying one of the previous methods twice: once as if the only given PSTL formula were φ_1 , and the other time as if the only given PSTL formula were φ_2 .

4.3 Multiple classes

In this section, we describe the generalization of our approach to the more general problem where the number of classes of time series is $k > 2$. Let us suppose to have a dataset of time series labeled with k values. The symbol \mathcal{S}_i represents the set of time series labeled by i , where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. The validity domain (with respect to a given PSTL formula φ) is represented by \mathcal{V}_i . We approximate all \mathcal{V}_i separately with one of the two

proposed methods. Then, for every label $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, the parameter valuation \hat{v}_i is chosen in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_i$ to maximize the distance from the union set of the other validity domains. Therefore, $\hat{v}_i = \arg \max_{v \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_i} d\left(v, \bigcup_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^k \hat{\mathcal{V}}_j\right)$, where d is the point-set distance defined in (1). Finally, for the classification purpose, in analogy with the binary case, we classify a signal \mathbf{x} into the class i such that $i = \arg \max_{j=1, \dots, k} \rho(\varphi_{\hat{v}_j}; \mathbf{x})$.

5 Application

We implemented our approach in the publicly available tool MiniPaSTeL³ (Mining Parameters for Signal Temporal Logic), leveraging the RTAMT tool [17] for monitoring STL formulas, and applied it to three case studies. We provide the scripts and the seeds to reproduce the results we present. We run the experiments on a MacBook Pro with 16 GB RAM and M1 processor. For each application, we report the set of mined STL specifications and the misclassification rate (MCR) achieved in the classification. Moreover, each case study focuses on seeking an answer to a research question:

RQ1 [Applicability] *Does the need for a PSTL template as input limit the applicability of our approach?* Our method requires the user to provide the PSTL template, but such a template may not be available or may be inadequate to discriminate between different classes. In such cases, we can interleave our approach with the human investigation to refine guesses for the PSTL template. The Aircraft Elevator case study illustrates how we can use the method to support the user in finding a suitable specification.

RQ2 [Performance evaluation] *How does our method compare to state-of-the-art?* We compare our approach to existing ones on the Naval dataset showing that it is comparable to or outperforms the state-of-the-art in terms of MCR. Moreover, we study how the MCR and the execution time vary with the number of training samples in the dataset.

RQ3 [Explainability of the results] *Can the user exploit the results to infer new insights into the traces?* The choice of parameter values in existing specification mining methods is generally carried out by applying off-the-shelf optimization techniques that minimize a given objective function without providing a general understanding of the values selection. Conversely, our method provides a visual understanding of how the parameters are selected by plotting (projections of) the validity domains. Thanks to that, it is possible to explain (unexpected) results, as shown in the Parking case study.

5.1 Aircraft Elevator

To answer **RQ1**, we consider the Simulink model of the Aircraft Elevator Control System [9], whose output signals report the position over time of the left elevator of the aircraft. We generated time series of two classes, \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 , by varying the parameters of the system input function: Fig. 2a depicts one representative signal per class.

We explore the workflow in which an engineer uses our approach to explore manually crafted templates and find one that discriminates well between two classes of signals.

³ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18JqnAzwzXNCag-PAYX6g1QNorIaFJZTv/view?usp=sharing>

By analyzing the shape of the time series in Fig. 2a, we observe that the signals from both classes are characterized by oscillations around the same values, but with different frequencies. In particular, the red one has a higher frequency than the blue one. To leverage this difference, we may design a specification that imposes that signals oscillate around the higher (unknown) value p for a certain (unknown) amount of time T . For each class, we learn the values p and T . We expect the signals of the two classes stabilizing around the same value with the interval of time for the time series in \mathcal{S}_1 longer than for time series in \mathcal{S}_2 . Thus, we consider the following PSTL template:

$$\varphi = \mathbf{G}\left((x \geq p) \rightarrow (\mathbf{G}_{[0,T]}|x - p| < 0.5)\right).$$

The formula φ expresses the behavior of signal x that remains “close” to the magnitude parameter p for T time units, immediately after the signal has become greater than p . We decided to manually set the notion of “closeness” to indicate a distance smaller than the value 0.5. This makes the validity domains 2-dimensional, giving the reader a better visual understanding of how the proposed methods work.

The parameter space is given by $\mathcal{W} = [0, 1000] \times [-1.6, 1.6]$. We impose the minimal sizes of cells in the parameter space to be $\mathbf{g} = (31.25, 0.1)$ to satisfy (5) for $k = 5$.

We then apply *FixedBin* method to compute the parameter valuations \hat{v}_1 and \hat{v}_2 . $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$, $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$, \hat{v}_1 , and \hat{v}_2 are shown in Fig. 2b: $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ is represented by the cyan region, $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$ by the red one (not visible because entirely subsumed by $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$), while the gray color represents their overlapping. The use of *AdaBin* method leads to the same approximations with the only difference that cells do not have all the same (minimal) size.

The mined parameter valuations are $\hat{v}_1 = (438, 1.0)$ and $\hat{v}_2 = (719, 1.6)$ for \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 , respectively, yielding the following specifications:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_1 : \varphi_{\hat{v}_1} &= \mathbf{G}((x \geq 1.0) \rightarrow (\mathbf{G}_{[0,438]}|x - 1.0| < 0.5)) \\ \mathcal{S}_2 : \varphi_{\hat{v}_2} &= \mathbf{G}((x \geq 1.6) \rightarrow (\mathbf{G}_{[0,719]}|x - 1.6| < 0.5)). \end{aligned}$$

We note that \hat{v}_2 belongs not only to $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$, but also to $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$. From Fig. 2b, we observe that this is inevitable: since $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$ is a subset of $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$, every parameter valuation $v \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2$ is also in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$, resulting in $d(v, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1) = 0$. Hence, the chosen φ cannot be instantiated to discriminate \mathcal{S}_2 from \mathcal{S}_1 . This observation suggests the PSTL formula should be changed to better discriminate between the two sets.

We then observe that φ requires the signal to remain close to p for at least T time units without specifying any condition about when the signal has to fall. Therefore, \mathcal{V}_1 includes \mathcal{V}_2 because the satisfaction of *high* values of T implies the satisfaction of *low* values of T . Therefore, we change the PSTL formula φ by adding the requirement that the signal has to move away from the value around which it oscillates after T_2 time units. Furthermore, to remain in the 2-dimensional parameter space for visualization reasons, we replace the parameter value p with the scalar value 1.1. As a result, the new PSTL template we define is:

$$\psi = \mathbf{G}\left((x \geq 1.1) \rightarrow (\mathbf{G}_{[0,T_1]}|x - 1.1| < 0.5 \wedge \mathbf{G}_{[T_2, T_2+T_1]}|x - 1.1| > 0.5)\right),$$

where T_1 is just a different symbol to indicate the parameter T in φ . In this case, both parameters T_1 and T_2 are temporal parameters, so the parameter space becomes $\mathcal{W} = [0, 1000] \times [0, 1000]$.

Fig. 2.

The approximations of validity domains with respect to the new template ψ are shown in Fig. 2c (this plot is done with *AdaBin* to show what the approximation with adaptive cell size looks like). We see that no validity domain subsumes the other one any longer, so it is possible to find parameter valuations discriminating one set of time series from the other one. The mined values are $\hat{v}_1 = (500, 500)$ and $\hat{v}_2 = (16, 47)$.

By studying the performances of φ and ψ as classifiers, we confirm the outcomes of the manual analysis carried out with the visualization of the validity domains. As expected, φ performs very poorly, with a MCR of 0.5 because all signals in \mathcal{S}_1 are misclassified in class 2; conversely, ψ achieves a MCR of 0.

To summarize, template-based techniques are usually employed when an engineer expects a certain behavior from the system and wants to extrapolate its numerical values. Nevertheless, this case study shows how our approach can be used not only to mine the desired parameters but also to help the engineer refine the PSTL template, providing a visual understanding of the differences between two signal classes. This observation opens up to processes in which the algorithm's executions and human investigation are interleaved: the engineer steers the search while the algorithm refines it.

5.2 Naval Surveillance

We use the naval surveillance dataset [12] to compare the performance of our methods to existing ones (**RQ2**). Since, to the best of our knowledge, there are no existing works focusing on parameter mining for STL to tackle the classification task, the only meaningful comparisons that are possible are with methods mining the whole STL formula.

The dataset contains 2000 2-dimensional signals describing the evolution over time of the coordinates of ships approaching a harbor; each signal contains 61 sample points.

Fig. 3 depicts the projection of some examples of the signal data set to the 2-dimensional spatial coordinates. The signals are partitioned into three different classes:

- *green* signals represent nominal behaviors in which ships arrive from the sea, get through the passage between the island and the peninsula, and reach the harbor.
- *red* signals describe anomalous trajectories of ships deviating to the island before heading towards the harbor (behavior relatable to human trafficking activities).
- *blue* signals depict ships that approach the passage between the island and the peninsula but that, at a certain point, turn around and go back to the open sea; this scenario could be connected to terrorist activities.

This dataset was mainly used for anomaly detection purposes, namely with the goal of discriminating the normal behavior from the two anomalous ones [4, 12, 16]. Similarly to authors in [15], we are rather interested in characterizing the three classes by discriminating each class from the other two. We consider the PSTL template mined in [16]: $\varphi = ((x_2 > p_2) \mathbf{U}_{[T_1, T_2]} (x_1 \leq p_1))$, where x_1 and x_2 are variables that refer to the first and second coordinate of

Fig. 3. Traces representing ship trajectories. The Figure has been redrawn from [12].

the signals, respectively. For each one of the three classes, we aim to find the parameter valuations for p_1 , p_2 , T_1 and T_2 that produce the most appropriate instantiation of φ .

We observe that φ is monotonic with respect to all its parameters (increasing with respect to T_2 and p_1 , and decreasing with respect to T_1 and p_2). Hence, we can apply the monotonic variant of our methods. The set of specifications generated using 150 training samples (50 for each class) is:

$$\text{Class 1 (green): } \varphi_{\hat{v}_1} = (x_2 > 22.44) \mathbf{U}_{[40, 245]} (x_1 \leq 27.37)$$

$$\text{Class 2 (red): } \varphi_{\hat{v}_2} = (x_2 > 20.63) \mathbf{U}_{[40, 75]} (x_1 \leq 42)$$

$$\text{Class 3 (blue): } \varphi_{\hat{v}_3} = (x_2 > 29.69) \mathbf{U}_{[110, 130]} (x_1 \leq 61.5).$$

We evaluate the classification performance of our method for each class by considering the misclassification rate (MCR), namely the number of misclassified signals over the total number of signals. MCR for class i is defined as $\text{MCR}_i := \frac{|\text{FN}_i| + |\text{FP}_i|}{\sum_{j=1}^k |\mathcal{S}_j|}$, where FN_i and FP_i correspond to the false negatives and false positives of class i , respectively.

Table 1 summarizes the results of average MCRs on the testing set over five different runs (different training samples are drawn at every run), the number of training and testing samples used and the computational time. We use Table 1 to first study how our method scales when varying the number of training samples and then to compare our approach with previous works in the literature.

As stated by Theorem 2, the complexity of *FixedBin* increases linearly with the increasing of the number of traces in the dataset; this is consistent with the experimental results reported in the first three rows of Table 1 and depicted in Figure 6 (see

Table 1. Comparison of MCR values (average and standard deviation, when available) with previous works on testing set, number of training and testing samples and computational time.

	# samples (train - test)	MCR ₁	MCR ₂	MCR ₃	Time (hours)
<i>FixedBin</i>	30 - 1970	0.04 ± 0.02	0.003 ± 0.003	0.04 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.02
<i>FixedBin</i>	90 - 1910	0.008 ± 0.008	0.002 ± 0.002	0.006 ± 0.006	1.71 ± 0.05
<i>FixedBin</i>	150 - 1850	0.02 ± 0.01	0.003 ± 0.002	0.02 ± 0.01	2.53 ± 0.07
<i>AdaBin</i>	150 - 1850	0.01 ± 0.02	0.002 ± 0.001	0.01 ± 0.02	3.7 ± 0.3
[4]	150 - 1850	0.008 ± 0.004	-	-	0.0001 ± 0.0001
[15]	150 - 1850	0.009 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.005	0.08 ± 0.07	0.53 ± 0.01
[16]	150 - 1850	0.52 ± 0.1	-	-	0.043 ± 0.001

Appendix). In terms of MCR, we would expect the performance to improve when increasing the number of traces in the training set; we observe that this trend is confirmed (*FixedBin* achieves better results with 150 signals than with 30), but not in a monotonic way, as *FixedBin* with 90 samples outperforms the other two.

To make a fair comparison with the existing works from the literature, we installed the tools presented in [4, 15, 16] on our laptop and ran them with the same training and testing samples. For [16] we could not reproduce the results reported in the paper and the MCR we obtained is very poor; conversely, the results achieved for [4, 15] are consistent with the values presented in the respective papers.

Our misclassification rates in classifying class 1 for *FixedBin* and *AdaBin* are slightly greater but still comparable with MCR₁ of [4, 15], while, for the second and third classes, our methods outperform the only method that tackled the multi-class classification problem. We remark that [15] addresses the multi-class classification problem as multiple binary classification problems. This means that three different classifiers are trained: one to distinguish class 1 from classes 2 and 3 together, a second for class 2 versus classes 1 and 3, and a third for class 3 versus classes 1 and 2. This is a common approach when tackling the multi-class classification problem, but, if no rules about how to combine the classifiers are presented, the prediction of the label of a new trace might be ambiguous: a trace might be unintentionally classified in several classes at the same time. Conversely, we combine different classifiers into a unique one discriminating among the three classes simultaneously.

Since both our methods approximate the entire validity domain before choosing the parameter values, the computational time is higher than the time required by other tools. Nevertheless, the approach we propose can be parallelized since the most expensive part corresponds to the computation of different validity domains that are independent, as independent are the different cells in the same validity domain.

5.3 Parking Scenario

In this case study, a vehicle is driving through a parking lot when a pedestrian walks out from behind a SUV onto the path of the ego vehicle. More specifically, the pedestrian walks in the x -direction at a speed of 1.5m/s, while the vehicle drives in an orthogonal y -direction with a constant velocity in the range [5.55, 11.11] mps (20-40 kph). The vehicle is equipped with an automatic emergency braking (AEB) function which brakes as hard as possible to avoid a collision with the pedestrian. We simulate the scenario

with CARLA 9.13, an open-source photo-realistic driving simulator for autonomous vehicle research [8]. An RGB camera is mounted on top of the vehicle and is equipped with YOLOv7, a state of the art image detection deep neural network [19]. We use the YOLOv7 model off-the-shelf and trigger an AEB procedure when there is an output with the label “person” with over 0.94 confidence probability (the threshold was set to completely eliminate false positives).

Since the AEB functionality is triggered through visual data, we have 3 different visual variations of the scenario: Time of day {day, night}, Clarity {clear, foggy}, Pedestrian type {adult, child}. For each combination, we collected 200 batches of data (coordinates of the position, velocity and acceleration of the car and the pedestrian). Fig. 4 shows two images extracted from the onboard camera for further illustration.

Suppose we are an engineer who wants to characterize the dynamics of two classes of data belonging to two opposite scenarios: an adult crossing the parking lot during the day versus a child pedestrian at night. Since each episode might end either with the vehicle braking and reaching a complete stop before hitting the pedestrian or with the vehicle crashing into the pedestrian, we start our analysis by providing the outcome of the episodes (crash or no crash) with an intuitive robustness measure. In particular, in the case of a non-crashing episode, we study the distance $d(t)$ of the car and the pedestrian over time. If we registered no crash, the car managed to stop in time, so $d(t)$ remains strictly positive throughout the whole episode. The greater the distance is, the safer the episode is (and vice versa). We translate the study of the distance between car and pedestrian as a function of the car’s velocity as the following PSTL template:

Fig. 4. Example of images extracted from the onboard camera of the vehicle. For illustration purpose, four pedestrians were placed in each scene. Left: scenario of a clear day with adult pedestrian. Right: scenario with foggy night and child.

$$\varphi_1 = \mathbf{G}(v_c(t) < v_{\text{no-crash}}) \rightarrow \mathbf{G}(d(t) \geq d_{\text{no-crash}}),$$

where $v_c(t)$ indicates the car’s velocity at time t , while $v_{\text{no-crash}}$ and $d_{\text{no-crash}}$ are the parameters to be mined.

Conversely, we can quantify the robustness of a crashing scenario by studying how strong the impact on the pedestrian is. To do so, we can either consider the car’s velocity at the moment of the crash or the distance the car would have required to stop after passing the crashing point. We opt for the latter option so that both the two measures of robustness are distances. Knowing the velocity v and the acceleration a (which is a deceleration) at the last frame before the crash, we apply basic notions of physics and estimate the distance D covered by the car before getting to a complete stop after passing the pedestrian’s y -position using the following relationship: $D = \frac{v^2}{2a}$. The greater D is, the stronger the impact is, and, consequently, the unsafer the scenario is. To study the

Fig. 5. Left and Middle: Approximation of validity domains for \mathcal{S}_1 in cyan and \mathcal{S}_2 in red (gray color is given by their overlapping) with respect to φ_1 (Left) and φ_2 (Middle). Right: Approximation of validity domains of \mathcal{S}_1 and $\bar{\mathcal{S}}_2$ with respect to φ_1 .

value of D as a function of the car's velocity, we consider the following PSTL template:

$$\varphi_2 = \mathbf{F}(v_c(t) > v_{\text{crash}}) \rightarrow (D \geq d_{\text{crash}}),$$

where $v_c(t)$ represents the car's velocity at time t , while v_{crash} and d_{crash} are the parameters to learn.

The quantification of the robustness of crashing and non-crashing episodes led to two PSTL templates. What would the engineer need to do now? Pick just one of the two templates? If our approach discriminated two classes using only one formula (as is always the case in the literature), the answer would be yes, but our approach allows different classes to be associated with different templates (Section 4.2). Guided by common sense, we judge the scenario taking place during the day and with the adult as pedestrian to be *safer* than the one by night with the child pedestrian since the greater visibility should allow the car to identify the pedestrian in advance (we will see later on that our method's output verifies the validity of this assumption). Since φ_1 describes a non-crashing episode, we associate it to the *safer* scenario - day and adult - whose class of data we indicate by \mathcal{S}_1 . Conversely, the crashing episode template φ_2 is used for the *unsafier* scenario - night and child - indicated by \mathcal{S}_2 .

We run the experiments with *FixedBin* (requiring 6.2 minutes in total) learning from the 80% of the dataset. Fig. 5a depicts (an approximation of) the validity domains of \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 with respect to φ_1 : parameter \hat{p}_1 is chosen in $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{S}_1, \varphi_1)$ to maximize the distance from $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{S}_2, \varphi_1)$. Similarly, Fig. 5b represents the validity domains with respect to φ_2 , where \hat{p}_2 is extracted in $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{S}_2, \varphi_2)$. The resulting specifications are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_1 : \varphi_{1, \hat{p}_1} &= \mathbf{G}(v_c(t) < 9.87) \rightarrow \mathbf{G}(d(t) \geq 1.18) \\ \mathcal{S}_2 : \varphi_{2, \hat{p}_2} &= \mathbf{F}(v_c(t) > 9.53) \rightarrow (D \geq 1.31). \end{aligned}$$

We combine φ_{1, \hat{p}_1} and φ_{2, \hat{p}_2} to predict the classification of the unseen set of traces (20% of the dataset) and we achieve a MCR of 0.037. In this application, all other tools perform worse: the MCR for [4] is 0.13, for [16] is 0.5, while [15] returns failure after

more than one hour and half of computation. Moreover, to answer **RQ3**, we observe that, apart from the classification itself, our approach provides additional insights into the case study thanks to the computation of the entire validity domains. For instance, by observing Fig. 5 (Left and Middle), the engineer gets the proof that \mathcal{S}_2 actually describes an *unsafier* scenario than \mathcal{S}_1 (for every velocity value, $d_{\text{no-crash}}$ is smaller for \mathcal{S}_2 , while d_{crash} is greater). In addition, the engineer finds out that the safety on non-crashing scenarios remains unchanged by varying the velocity in the range $[6, 7.5]$ mps ($d_{\text{no-crash}}$ remains, indeed, around 5 meters for the day-adult scenario and 3 meters for the night-child one), but it falls abruptly when the velocity overcomes the threshold of 7.5 mps (≈ 27 kph). Finally, the knowledge of the entire validity domains allows the engineer to easily add restrictions on the parameters to be learned (e.g., increasing the lower bound of $d_{\text{no-crash}}$ from one meter to two meters to enhance safety).

So far, we compared the scenarios of an adult pedestrian crossing the parking lot during the day versus a child pedestrian at night, both with a clear sky. What would happen if the latter scenario had foggy weather instead? Our human experience would consider the fog as a factor that decreases visibility and, consequently, increases the danger. To check this hypothesis, we run new experiments with the second class of data $\bar{\mathcal{S}}_2$ representing traces collected in a foggy night and with a child pedestrian. The MCR value we obtain now is 0.15, significantly greater than before (the other tools achieved the following MCRs: 0.11 for [4], 0.5 for [16], failure for [15]). Without any additional insights, we would not be able to understand the reason behind this unintuitive result: we would have expected a decrease in the MCR due to a larger gap in safety between the two classes caused by the presence of fog. By comparing Fig. 5a with Fig. 5c, we observe that the addition of fog produces the expansion of the validity domain of $\bar{\mathcal{S}}_2$ with respect to φ_1 , meaning that the vehicle manages to stop further from the pedestrian than in the limpid scenario. Consequently, the foggy scenario is actually safer and therefore less distinguishable from \mathcal{S}_1 . By manually inspecting the CARLA simulations, we confirmed this analysis by noticing that the fog added some visual noise masking the pedestrian, but in fact also accentuated their contour. The latter effect made the pedestrians more easily recognizable for YOLO. In conclusion, thanks to the insights provided by our method, we discovered that our human intuition for which the fog renders a pedestrian less visible does not hold in the CARLA simulation environment.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

We presented a new approach to mine parameters of arbitrary PSTL templates to perform multi-class classification tasks over time series data. We proposed two variants of the mining procedure, providing a statistical guarantee of optimality for the mined parameters. We validated the applicability of our approach in three case studies by demonstrating how to leverage our method’s outputs to refine the PSTL template or infer new insights into the data and by comparing our performances with the state-of-the-art.

The approach proposed in this paper is passive - the specification is mined with respect to a set of existing signals. We plan to explore the active learning approach and devise a testing strategy that can help inferring a representative specification that explains well the examples.

Acknowledgements This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 956123 (FOCETA). This preprint has not undergone peer review (when applicable) or any post-submission improvements or corrections. The Version of Record of this contribution is published in LNCS 14245, and is available online at <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44267-4>

References

1. Asarin, E., Donzé, A., Maler, O., Nickovic, D.: Parametric identification of temporal properties. In: Proc. of RV 2011. LNCS, vol. 7186, pp. 147–160. Springer (2011). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-29860-8_12
2. Bartocci, E., Bortolussi, L., Sanguinetti, G.: Data-driven statistical learning of temporal logic properties. In: Proc. of FORMATS. LNCS, vol. 8711, pp. 23–37. Springer (2014). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10512-3_3
3. Bartocci, E., Mateis, C., Nesterini, E., Nickovic, D.: Survey on mining signal temporal logic specifications. *Inf. Comput.* **289**(Part), 104957 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ic.2022.104957>
4. Bombara, G., Vasile, C.I., Penedo, F., Yasuoka, H., Belta, C.: A decision tree approach to data classification using signal temporal logic. In: Proc. of HSCC 2016. pp. 1–10. ACM (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2883817.2883843>
5. Bortolussi, L., Gallo, G.M., Křetínský, J., Nenzi, L.: Learning model checking and the kernel trick for signal temporal logic on stochastic processes. In: Proc. of TACAS 2022. LNCS, vol. 13243, pp. 281–300. Springer (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99524-9_15
6. Bufo, S., Bartocci, E., Sanguinetti, G., Borelli, M., Lucangelo, U., Bortolussi, L.: Temporal logic based monitoring of assisted ventilation in intensive care patients. In: Proc. of ISOLA 2014. LNCS, vol. 8803, pp. 391–403. Springer (2014). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-45231-8_30
7. Donzé, A., Ferrère, T., Maler, O.: Efficient robust monitoring for STL. In: Sharygina, N., Veith, H. (eds.) Proc. of CAV 2013. LNCS, vol. 8044, pp. 264–279. Springer (2013). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-39799-8_19
8. Dosovitskiy, A., Ros, G., Codevilla, F., Lopez, A., Koltun, V.: CARLA: An open urban driving simulator. In: Proc. of CoRL. PMLR, vol. 78, pp. 1–16 (2017). <http://proceedings.mlr.press/v78/dosovitskiy17a.html>
9. Ghidellaand, J., Mosterman, P.: Requirements-based testing in aircraft control design. In: AIAA Modeling and Simulation Technologies Conference and Exhibit. pp. 1–11 (08 2005). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2005-5886>
10. Hoxha, B., Dokhanchi, A., Fainekos, G.E.: Mining parametric temporal logic properties in model-based design for cyber-physical systems. *STTT* **20**(1), 79–93 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10009-017-0447-4>
11. Jha, S., Tiwari, A., Seshia, S.A., Sahai, T., Shankar, N.: TeLEx: Learning signal temporal logic from positive examples using tightness metric. *Formal Methods in System Design* **54**(3), 364–387 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10703-019-00332-1>
12. Kong, Z., Jones, A., Belta, C.: Temporal Logics for Learning and Detection of Anomalous Behavior. *IEEE Trans. Aut. Control* **62**(3), 1210–1222 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.2016.2585083>

13. Linard, A., Torre, I., Leite, I., Tumova, J.: Inference of multi-class stl specifications for multi-label human-robot encounters. In: 2022 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS). pp. 1305–1311 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS47612.2022.9982088>
14. Maler, O., Nickovic, D.: Monitoring temporal properties of continuous signals. In: Proc. of FORMATS 2004 and FTRTFT 2004. LNCS, vol. 3253, pp. 152–166. Springer (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1007/b100824>
15. Mohammadinejad, S., Deshmukh, J.V., Puranic, A.G., Vazquez-Chanlatte, M., Donzé, A.: Interpretable classification of time-series data using efficient enumerative techniques. In: Proc. of HSCC 2020. pp. 9:1–9:10. ACM (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3365365.3382218>
16. Nenzi, L., Silvetti, S., Bartocci, E., Bortolussi, L.: A robust genetic algorithm for learning temporal specifications from data. In: Proc. of QEST 2018. LNCS, vol. 11024, pp. 323–338. Springer (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99154-2_20
17. Nickovic, D., Yamaguchi, T.: RTAMT: online robustness monitors from STL. In: Proc. of ATVA 2020. LNCS, vol. 12302, pp. 564–571. Springer (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59152-6_34
18. Wald, A.: Sequential Tests of Statistical Hypotheses, pp. 256–298. Springer New York, New York, NY (1992). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-0919-5_18
19. Wang, C.Y., Bochkovskiy, A., Liao, H.Y.M.: YOLOv7: Trainable bag-of-freebies sets new state-of-the-art for real-time object detectors. arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.02696 (2022)
20. Xu, Z., Julius, A.A.: Census signal temporal logic inference for multiagent group behavior analysis. IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering **15**(1), 264–277 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASE.2016.2611536>
21. Younes, H.L.S., Simmons, R.G.: Probabilistic verification of discrete event systems using acceptance sampling. In: Proc. of CAV 2002. LNCS, vol. 2404, p. 223–235. Springer (2002). https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45657-0_17

A Proofs

Lemma 1 (Choice of N). *Let \mathcal{V} be a validity domain, C a cell not included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ based on N random samples. If $N \geq \log_{1-p_0}(\alpha)$ with $p_0, \alpha \in (0, 1)$, then the probability that C contains points in \mathcal{V} is smaller than p_0 with confidence $1 - \alpha$.*

Proof. Let us suppose to compute the over-approximation $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ of the validity domain \mathcal{V} by adding a cell to $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ if and only if at least one of the parameter valuations inside the cell belongs to the real validity domain. In applying this technique, we need a stopping criterion when no satisfied parameter valuations are found in a cell. This criterion is related to the number of parameter valuations to be examined before classifying a cell as not part of the validity domain.

With this goal in mind, let us briefly describe the *sequential probability ratio test*, introduced by Wald in [18]. The main idea is to perform the classical hypothesis testing with a number of samples not fixed in advance and that is shown to be minimal. Let H_0 denote the null hypothesis, H_1 the alternative hypothesis, α and β be the upper bounds for error of Type I and II, respectively. The test consists in iteratively drawing a sample and evaluating the corresponding likelihood ratio, given by the likelihood under the alternative hypothesis divided by the likelihood under the null hypothesis.

- If the value of the ratio is greater than the quantity $A(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1-\beta}{\alpha}$, the alternative hypothesis H_1 is accepted and the test stops;
- If the value of the ratio is smaller than the value $B(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta}{1-\alpha}$, the null hypothesis H_0 is accepted and the test stops;
- If none of the previous conditions is satisfied, a new sample is drawn and the procedure is repeated.

In our case, we use the *sequential probability ratio test* to compute the minimum number N of unsatisfied parameter valuations that we need to evaluate in a cell, before concluding with confidence $1 - \alpha$ that the proportion of satisfied parameter valuations of the cell is smaller than $p_0 \cdot 100\%$, for a chosen value of $p_0 \in (0, 1)$. If, while doing the N evaluations, we find one satisfied parameter valuation, the *sequential probability ratio test* is not required anymore, since we are sure there exists at least one satisfied parameter valuation in the cell and, therefore, we can add the cell to the approximation of the validity domain.

Let $p \cdot 100\%$ be the unknown true proportion of satisfied parameter valuations of the cell. The null hypothesis (that we aim to reject) is that the value of p is greater than a predefined threshold $p_0 \in (0, 1)$, namely $H_0 : p \geq p_0$. On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis (that we aim to accept) is that the proportion of satisfied parameter valuations in the cell under study is zero, namely $H_1 : p = 0$. The region $(0, p_0)$ is called *indifference region* and it must be non-empty in order to freely choose α and β . If H_2 is the hypothesis that neither H_0 nor H_1 holds, i.e., $H_2 : p \in (0, p_0)$, then the following results are guaranteed [21]:

$$\begin{cases} Pr[H_0 \text{ holds} \mid \text{accept } H_1] & \leq \alpha, \\ Pr[H_1 \text{ holds} \vee H_2 \text{ holds} \mid \text{accept } H_1] & \geq 1 - \alpha. \end{cases}$$

In the following, a sample s corresponds to a parameter valuation and its value is 1 if the parameter valuation renders the formula satisfied, 0 otherwise. When r samples have been drawn and all of them are unsatisfied, the likelihood ratio is given by:

$$\frac{p_{1,r}}{p_{0,r}} = \frac{P(s_1 = 0, \dots, s_r = 0 \mid p = 0)}{\max_{p_0 \leq \bar{p} \leq 1} P(s_1 = 0, \dots, s_r = 0 \mid p = \bar{p})} = \frac{1}{\max_{p_0 \leq \bar{p} \leq 1} \binom{r}{0} \bar{p}^0 (1 - \bar{p})^{(r-0)}} = \frac{1}{(1 - p_0)^r}.$$

In order to satisfy $\frac{p_{1,r}}{p_{0,r}} \geq A$, it is therefore sufficient to choose $N = r \geq \log_{(1-p_0)} \left(\frac{1}{A} \right) = \log_{(1-p_0)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\beta} \right)$. We can set β (i.e., the error of Type II) to zero because it corresponds to the situation in which H_1 holds but we have accepted H_0 . However, we never accept H_0 since we stop the sequential test and include a cell to the over-approximation as soon as we find one satisfied parameter valuation. This is due to the fact that we do not need to accept $p \geq p_0$ to include a cell in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$, but it is enough that $p > 0$. This condition is true for sure once a satisfied valuation has been found (this also automatically excludes the possibility that H_1 holds).

In conclusion, the evaluation of a cell is carried out by evaluating at most $\log_{(1-p_0)} (\alpha)$ parameter valuations.

Before proving Theorem 1, let us consider some preliminary results.

Lemma 2. *Triangle inequality holds for function D , namely $\forall \mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2, \mathcal{V}_3$ such that \mathcal{V}_i is a bounded set in \mathbb{R}^m for $i = 1, 2, 3$,*

$$D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_3) + D(\mathcal{V}_3, \mathcal{V}_2).$$

The result is known but we provide a sketch of the proof for completeness sake.

Proof. Given $\varepsilon > 0$, for each \mathbf{v}_1 in \mathcal{V}_1 there must exist a point $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_2$ in \mathcal{V}_2 such that $\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon$. This is due to the fact that, for each \mathbf{v}_1 in \mathcal{V}_1 ,

$$\inf_{\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathcal{V}_2} \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) = d(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2).$$

So, for every $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon \geq \inf_{\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathcal{V}_2} \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) + \varepsilon \geq \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_2)$$

for a certain $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_2$ in \mathcal{V}_2 . Therefore, given $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 > 0$, for each \mathbf{v}_1 in \mathcal{V}_1 there exist $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_2$ in \mathcal{V}_2 and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_3$ in \mathcal{V}_3 such that:

$$\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_2) \leq \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_3) + \text{dist}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_3, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_3) + \varepsilon_1 + D(\mathcal{V}_3, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon_2,$$

where the first inequality holds because dist is the Euclidean distance. Hence,

$$\inf_{\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathcal{V}_2} \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) \leq \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_3) + D(\mathcal{V}_3, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2.$$

Since the previous inequality holds for any $\mathbf{v}_1 \in \mathcal{V}_1$, the following inequality is also satisfied

$$D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) = \sup_{\mathbf{v}_1 \in \mathcal{V}_1} \inf_{\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathcal{V}_2} \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_3) + D(\mathcal{V}_3, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2.$$

Since the inequality holds for arbitrary $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 > 0$, the thesis is proven.

Lemma 3. $D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_i, \mathcal{V}_i) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$, for $i = 1, 2$.

Proof. For simplicity of notation, let us consider $i = 1$. Let us pick a generic point $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$; we want to prove that $d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_1) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. If $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}_1$, then $d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_1) = 0 \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. Otherwise, $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1 \setminus \mathcal{V}_1$. Since $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$, the whole cell $C_{\mathbf{v}}$ to which \mathbf{v} belongs to is included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ (\mathbf{v} may belong to several cells if it is a point on the border; in this case, at least one of these cells must be included in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$). According to the procedure applied in our methods, a cell is included in the approximation $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ of the validity domain \mathcal{V}_1 only if at least one of its point belongs to \mathcal{V}_1 . Let us name \mathbf{w} the point in $C_{\mathbf{v}}$ that belongs to \mathcal{V}_1 . Since the maximum distance between two points in the same cell having size \mathbf{g} is $\|\mathbf{g}\|$, it follows that $\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. Therefore,

$$d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_1) = \inf\{\text{dist}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}) \mid \mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{V}_1\} \leq \text{dist}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|.$$

We proved that for all $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$, $d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_1) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. This implies that $\sup\{d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_1) \mid \mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1\} \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. The conclusion holds because the left hand side of the previous inequality corresponds to the definition of $D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \mathcal{V}_1)$.

Theorem 1 (Optimality). Let \mathcal{V}_1 and \mathcal{V}_2 be the validity domains for classes \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . Let $i \in \{1, 2\}$, \mathbf{v}_i^* be an optimal parameter valuation for class i , $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_i$ be the approximation of \mathcal{V}_i using cell resolution given by vector $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^m$, $N \geq \log_{1-p_0}(\alpha)$, and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ the parameter valuation found with FixedBin. Then, the difference of the distances from $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ and from \mathbf{v}_i^* to the other class validity domain is bounded by the cell resolution:

$$|d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i, \mathcal{V}_{(i \bmod 2)+1}) - d(\mathbf{v}_i^*, \mathcal{V}_{(i \bmod 2)+1})| \leq \|\mathbf{g}\| \quad (4)$$

with probability $1 - p_0$ and confidence $1 - \alpha$.

Proof. Let us first prove $d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) - d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$. We observe that:

$$d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq D(\mathcal{V}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1) + D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2, \mathcal{V}_2), \quad (6)$$

where the last inequality is obtained by the double application of triangle inequality for function D (Lemma 2).

From Lemma 1, we deduce that the probability that $D(\mathcal{V}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1) = 0$ is $1 - p_0$ with confidence $1 - \alpha$ since it is a consequence of $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ being an over-approximation of \mathcal{V}_1 . In addition, $D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$ for Lemma 3. Moreover, since $D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) = \sup\{d(\mathbf{v}, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) \mid \mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1\}$, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there must exist $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ such that $D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) \leq d(\mathbf{v}, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + \varepsilon$. We remind also that $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1$ was chosen in $\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$ such that $d(\mathbf{v}, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) \leq d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2)$ for every $\mathbf{v} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}_1$. Proceeding from (6), we obtain therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) &\leq D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_2, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq d(\mathbf{v}, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + \varepsilon + \|\mathbf{g}\| \leq \\ &d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + \varepsilon + \|\mathbf{g}\| \leq d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + D(\mathcal{V}_2, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) + \varepsilon + \|\mathbf{g}\| = \\ &d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon + \|\mathbf{g}\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality holds in probability since $D(\mathcal{V}_2, \hat{\mathcal{V}}_2) = 0$, as previously described for \mathcal{V}_1 . Since $d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) - d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\| + \varepsilon$ holds for every ε , the thesis is proven.

Let us now prove that $d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) - d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq \|\mathbf{g}\|$.

$$\begin{aligned} d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) - d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2) &\leq d(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) - D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon \stackrel{\text{Def of } D \text{ in (2)}}{\leq} \\ &D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) - D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) + \varepsilon \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2}}{\leq} \\ &D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \mathcal{V}_1) + \overline{D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2)} - \overline{D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2)} + \varepsilon = \\ &D(\hat{\mathcal{V}}_1, \mathcal{V}_1) + \varepsilon \stackrel{\text{Lemma 3}}{\leq} \|\mathbf{g}\| + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

where the first inequality holds for every $\varepsilon > 0$ for definition of supremum and for the choice of \mathbf{v}_1^* : $D(\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2) - \varepsilon \leq d(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{V}_2) \leq d(\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathcal{V}_2)$.

Theorem 2 (Complexity). Let n be the total number of signals and let m be the number of different parameter symbols in the PSTL template φ . Let $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^m$ be the vector that contains the minimal sizes of the cells and let the parameter space be

$\mathcal{W} = \prod_{i=1}^m [a_i, b_i]$ as in Eq. (3). Then, the total number L of monitors is exponential in m and linear in n . In particular,

$$L \leq \left(\max_{i=1, \dots, m} \left\lceil \frac{b_i - a_i}{g_i} \right\rceil \right)^m \cdot (N \cdot n) = \mathcal{O}(M^m) \cdot \mathcal{O}(n),$$

where N is the maximum number of parameter valuations to be evaluated in every cell and M is a suitable positive number.

Proof. The total number c of cells needed to approximate \mathcal{W} is given by:

$$c = \prod_{i=1}^m \left\lceil \frac{b_i - a_i}{g_i} \right\rceil \leq \left(\max_{i=1, \dots, m} \left\lceil \frac{b_i - a_i}{g_i} \right\rceil \right)^m, \quad (7)$$

which is therefore exponential in the number of parameters m and does not depend on the number of time series n . In every cell, the total number l of monitored formulas is proportional to the number of time series n . In particular, $l \leq N \cdot n$, where N is the maximum number of parameter valuations to be evaluated in every cell (the choice of N is done according to Lemma 1). In conclusion, from $L \leq c \cdot l \leq c \cdot N \cdot n$ and the replacement of c with (7), the thesis is proven.

The linear dependence of the complexity with respect to the number of signals n stated by Theorem 2 is consistent with the results obtained in the *Naval* case study (Section 5.2), whose values are reported in Table 1 and depicted in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Plot of the computational time (hours) as a function of the number of traces in the training set for the *Naval* case study